

Vision por computador

1 introducción y motivación

Que es vision artificial?

What is computer vision?

Computer
vision
according to
Hollywood

What is computer vision?

Making useful decisions about real physical objects and scenes based on images (Shapiro & Stockman, 2001)

Extracting descriptions of the world from pictures or sequences of pictures (Forsyth & Ponce, 2003)

Analyzing images and producing descriptions that can be used to interact with the environment (Horn, 1986)

Designing representations and algorithms for relating images to models of the world (Ballard & Brown, 1982)

Visual processing in the brain

where pathway
(dorsal stream)

V1

Pre-frontal
cortex

what pathway
(ventral stream)

Vision as measurement device

Pollefeys et al.

Goesele et al.

Vision as a source of semantic information

Slide credit: Kristen Grauman

Cómo se relaciona con otras disciplinas

Computer
Vision

Machine
Learning
Deep Learning

Deep Learning
Hardware
Platforms

Recommender
Systems

Natural
Language
Processing

Computer
Graphics

Artificial
Intelligence

Speech
Recognition

Data Mining

Text Mining

What is it related to?

Un poco de historia

Computer vision and Applications

El problema intrínseco

Imagen digital

2D arrays (matrices) of numbers:

If color image, we have 3 arrays - red, green, blue

Dificultad intrínseca

Tratamos de inferir conceptos a partir de números sin estructura aparente

File									
146	161	165	159	165	177	166	142	143	141
149	154	152	149	158	171	164	147	144	141
147	146	145	148	157	160	151	139	140	138
147	149	157	167	167	155	139	129	133	132
148	154	167	176	169	150	135	131	131	131
139	144	152	155	149	139	133	133	133	134
131	132	132	131	132	133	131	127	130	132
133	132	129	127	134	141	134	122	125	127
129	127	126	128	131	132	130	127	129	127
129	127	126	128	131	132	130	128	130	129

El hombro de la vaca

An image as a function

Bright regions are high, dark regions are low

The goal of computer vision

- To bridge the gap between pixels and “meaning”

What we see

0	3	2	5	4	7	6	9	8
3	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2	1	0	3	2	5	4	7	6
5	2	3	0	1	2	3	4	5
4	3	2	1	0	3	2	5	4
7	4	5	2	3	0	1	2	3
6	5	4	3	2	1	0	3	2
9	6	7	4	5	2	3	0	1
8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0

What a computer sees

Source: S. Narasimhan

Thorpe, et al. *Nature*, 1996

Thorpe, et al. *Nature*, 1996

Los problemas semánticos

“There was a table set out under a tree in front of the house, and the March Hare and the Hatter were having tea at it.”

“The table was a large one, but the three were all crowded together at one corner of it ...”

From “A Mad Tea-Party”
Alice's Adventures in Wonderland
by
Lewis Carroll

Illustration by **Arthur Rackham**

Computer vision

Computer vision

Computer vision

Computer vision

Object recognition and categorization

Classification:

Is this an forest?

Classification:

Does this image contain a building? [yes/no]

Detection:

Does this image contain a car? [where?]

Detection:

Which objects do this image contain? [where?]

Detection:

Accurate localization (segmentation)

Detection:

Estimating 3D geometrical properties

Activity understanding

Activity understanding

Los "challenges" semánticos

Challenges: viewpoint variation

Challenges: illumination

Challenges: scale

slide credit: Fei-Fei, Fergus & Torralba

Challenges: deformation

Challenges: occlusion

Magritte, 1957

slide credit: Fei-Fei, Fergus & Torralba

Challenges: background clutter

Kilmeny Niland. 1995

segmentation

Challenges: object intra-class variation

slide credit: Fei-Fei, Fergus & Torralba

Change blindness

Rensink, O'regan, Simon, etc.